

Ihya'u Sunnah wa Ikhmadul Bid'ah

also known as “إحياء السنة وإخماد البدعة”, “The Revival of the Sunna and Destruction of Innovation”

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Entry tags: فقه, Uthmaniyah, Religious Group, Islamic Theology, Text, Shari'a, Islamic Traditions, Islamic Revival, Sunni

The book was written by Sheikh Uthman ibn Fodio, (a Religious reformer) who established Sokoto Caliphate, and composed it to serve as religious text used by the citizens of the caliphate and others in the present generation.

Date Range: 1754 CE - 1817 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

–Source 1: Uthman ibn Fodio (nd). *Ihya'u Sunnah wa Ikhmadu al-Bid'ah*. Abdullahi Yassar Printing press, Kano Nigeria.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

–Source 1 URL: <https://ia804700.us.archive.org/6/items/amnsegnamnsegn/isib.pdf>

–Source 1 Description: <https://tribuneonlineng.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/fodiyo-1.jpg>

–Source 2 URL:

https://m.timbu.com/poi/986/102430_danfodiostomb_w_jpg12d0b5d78bdf50026ff006a30b3a7c5e-986-577c1b7af28a5.

–Source 2 Description:

https://www.nairaland.com/attachments/10000882_9jupmj1vpigdepd_jpeg_jpege561f762495aca34d90bfff8de032

–Source 3 URL: <https://m.timbu.com/poi/986/she-986-577c1b8f64854.jpg>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

- ↳ Number of sheets
 - Multiple sheets

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: It was written on a normal paper sheet

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- ↳ Tomb
 - No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No

- ↳ Temple
 - No

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- ↳ Shrine
 - No
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - Yes
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: Personal use by individuals

Notes: It was also kept in some formal and traditional schools.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: Nothing like that, only a simple description of the text was placed to identify the text within the rest of the text.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: There might be an indirect funding due to the position of the Sheikh as the leader of the caliphate.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The polity ensured the smooth running and services of the religious center that was devoted to imparting the knowledge contained in the text

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: Leaders of the polity served as the religious leaders in the region

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some political officials usually contribute to the production of such a text.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: They actively supported the development of institutional networks.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: They usually encourage religious observance and moral practices stipulated in the text

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

Notes: The legal code of the caliphate is derived from the directives of the text.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: At that time usually, the production of the text is done by a religious specialist.

↳ Present full-time?

– No

Notes: They engage in other activities apart from the production of the text.

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Notes: Religious specialists belong to both sexes (male and female), such as Asma'u (daughter of Sheikh Uthman) who is considered among the prominent Islamic scholars and many other women at that time.

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
 - Notes: The specialty of religion is not restricted to a tribe or ethnic group, even though the most dominant people belong to the Fulani/Hausa tribe at that time.

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No
 - Notes: They are not restricted to special classes.

- ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - Yes
 - Notes: They are dedicated in addition to other business setups to earn means of livelihood.

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - Yes
 - Notes: There is a hierarchy among the religious specialist arranged on the order of Sheikh, Malam Students, etc.

- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
 - No

- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Various schools and other educational institutions are established to ensure the training of religious specialists

- ↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Formal educational Institutions were established in the caliphate to train and impart knowledge to the public.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Observance of religious activities is expected to be in accordance with the stipulation of the text.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: The text is subject to moderation once an error or mistake is observed

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

Notes: Any specialist can interpret the text without any restriction

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

Notes: Any specialist can transmit the book

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: Any directive quoted from the Qur'an can not be altered

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the cannon as it is currently understood?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Notes: It was written in the Arabic language, which was the language of the Holy Qur'an

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

Notes: The language of the book is not considered endogenous, for the presence of the dominant language of Fulani and Hausa in the region.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Arabic language is associated to the Islamic religious specialists.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

Notes: He said love the Arabic language for it is my language and language of the Qur'an and shall be the language of the people of Paradise.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: They usually use Hausa and Fulani Languages to teach the contents of the text.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Notes: The text of the book is continuously reproduced for the use of the people over generations

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

–Total audience: 1000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

–Number: 300000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 50000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 1000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Migration, Birthrate and Death rate.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

–Number: 50

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 2

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 58

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Migration

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

–Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

–Small religious group (trying to be organized-controlled by larger religious group)

–Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: There are many non Muslims who were simultaneously being converted to Islam and add up to the population of the followers.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Effort to convert others to the religion of the text is encouraged to all

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Is rewarded as Prophet (SAW) said to Ali (May Allah be pleased with him), "By Allah, if a single person is guided by Allah through you, it will be better for you than a whole load of red camels".

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Paradise is promised to them in the hereafter

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: No, The Almighty Allah said in the Holy Qur'an "There shall be no compulsion in [acceptance of] the Religion" Qur'an 02:256

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: It encouraged proselytization

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The author was a reformist and revivalist at his time, and he wrote the book with the ambition of reforming the practices of the people towards observing the teaching of the Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and eradicating innovations.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Yes

Notes: The text contains verses and traditions of the Prophet (SAW) which are full of healings for spiritual, psychological, and physical diseases.

- ↳ Physical healing
 - Yes
- ↳ Mental/psychological healing
 - Yes
- ↳ Incubation
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text served as cleansing because it purifies Muslims from the religious innovations to the light of Sunnah.
- ↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
 - No
- ↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
 - No
- ↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
 - Yes
 - Notes: There is moral significance attached to the materiality of the text.
 - ↳ Specify
 - Specify: Moral ethics are presented in the text
- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?
 - Please specify the substances in the sub-questions
 - No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are copies made on the translation of the text to other languages

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– I don't know

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text is single copy

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Other

–Other [specify]: It contained many verses and traditions from the Qur'an and Hadith

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text served as a guide on how to perform some ritual services such as Prayer, Funeral, etc

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text expressed the legal code expected to be applied by the adherents of Islam within the caliphate

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– No

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: It analyzed some ethics to be applied by the judges

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– No

↳ Exile?

– No

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: There is determined corporal punishment for those to have committed fornication

↳ Ostracism?

– No

↳ Seizure of property?

– No

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ Grants of property?

– Yes

Notes: Grant of booty for those to have participated in Jihad

↳ Social promotion?

– Yes

Notes: The person to have studied the text and put its directives into practice is considered at a high rank worthy of emulation by others.

↳ Financial rewards?

– No

↳ Implied financial rewards (tax exemption?)?

– No

↳ Grants of labor?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The applied calendar in the text was Hijrah Lunar Calendar

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

Notes: It did not state time of planting

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– Yes

Notes: It directed water management for the purpose of performing Ibadat and daily activities

- ↳ Harvest?
 - No

- ↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It determined the seventh day of a born baby as the time of his naming ceremony

- ↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)
 - Yes
 - Notes: It directed that first haircuts be done on the seventh day of his born

- ↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?
 - No

- ↳ Marriage?
 - Yes
 - Notes: there is a special chapter dedicated to marriage in the text

- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - Yes

- ↳ Divorce?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It set a guide to divorce when necessary

- ↳ Warfare?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It guided for warfare when it became necessary

- ↳ Funerary services?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It set directives on funerary services, as a chapter was identified for that

- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Guides to trade and commerce are pointed out in the text

- ↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: 2

Notes: The festivals are for Id prayers that occur yearly

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 2000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– No

Notes: Food consumption is for all members of the community

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

Notes: Pilgrimage is obligatory for those who are capable of doing so.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: Many reasons are behind writing the text apart from pilgrimage

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– No

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?
– Yes

↳ Feasting?
– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?
– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?
– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?
– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?
– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?
– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?
– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?
– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?
– Generally positive

- ↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?
 - Specify: There must be a detail which are to be associated with psychology

- ↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?
 - No

- ↳ Are debates framed in other ways?
 - No

- ↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?
 - No

- ↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?
 - I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It confirmed belief in the afterlife, as pointed out in the attached page

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?
 - No

 - ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?
 - No

 - ↳ Afterlife in "other" space?
 - Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

↳ Personal effects?

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: No other funerary ritual in the text

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: He is self sufficient

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: His knowledge extends to the entire domain of Human affairs

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Presence of creations exhibit His power and presence

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Especially Prophets and Messengers of God

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through divine revelation to Messengers

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are present

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The text identified Angels and Jinns among the supernatural beings different from the humans

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– No

Notes: Angels can furnish on the directives of Allah

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes
Notes: Only jinns possess hunger, unlike Angels who do not.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Movements from one place to another

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?
– No

Are other categories of beings present?
– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?
– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

- ↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Specify: It care about every living being

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
– No

↳ At specified time in future
– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future
– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future
– Yes

↳ At some other time [specify]
– Yes
Notes: Knowledge of the time is only belongs to Allah

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
– No

↳ Divine judgment event
– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world
– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
– No

↳ Establishment of new political system
– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system
– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Belief in the paradise and Hell

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: None could survive the eschaton

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes

- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Especially in giving out Zakat

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 20000

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 2

Notes: Timely barriers existed between one service to another

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: It presented discuss on the sacrifice of Animals

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Is mandatory for those having the stipulated amount

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: such as precious metals and money

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Such as cows, sheep, Camels, and Goats

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– Yes

- ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - No
- ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Only sick are not allowed to be given in zakat
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By the community?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By specific individuals?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It specified mandatory attendance to the daily congregation of prayers and other terminal services
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it required?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Maintenance of the place of worship is a responsibility to all

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

- A city-state

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

- A Segmentary Lineage

Notes: Rivals of the sheikh attempted to destruct the text

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

- Yes

Notes: The text encouraged alms giving to relieve poverty and famine effects among people

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

- Yes

Notes: It institutionalized alms giving

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

- Yes

Notes: the text encourage care for the elderly and infirm

Other forms of welfare?

- Yes

Notes: Mutual assistance among the people

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

- Yes

Notes: Many schools are known for teaching of the text

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

- No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The entire life affairs are considered religious

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Education is meant for all

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Is not restricted to any gender

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Should be respected in the community

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Mining

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

Notes: Encourage agricultural practices

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]
– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Gathering